

EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT AS A DETERMINANT OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG STAFF NURSES IN LEVEL III GOVERNMENT HOSPITALS IN CENTRAL LUZON, PHILIPPINES

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Abstract

The study aimed to ascertain Emotional Quotient as determinant of job satisfaction among staff nurses in Level III government hospitals in Central Luzon, Philippines. It utilized a quantitative approach of research, particularly descriptive-evaluative, descriptive-comparative, and descriptive-correlational designs to ascertain emotional quotient as prognosticator of job satisfaction among staff nurses in the four Level III government hospitals in Central Luzon. Data were collected from 605 staff nurses employed in the four Level III Government Hospitals in Central Luzon using the adopted instruments from Genos Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire of Spector. Nurses agreed moderately on their job satisfaction towards supervision (4.56), co-workers (WM=4.53). The nurse-respondents agreed slightly on promotion (WM=3.79), fringe benefits (3.73), nature of work (3.81) and operating conditions (4.08), and communication (WM=3.90). They disagreed slightly on contingent reward WM= (3.15) and pay (WM=2.53). There was a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Job Satisfaction, Staff Nurses, Philippines.

INTRODUCTION

The nursing profession deals with challenges that are out of control, and sometimes patients' lives are at stake. Through their vocation, nurses have many duties and often face adversities. These include physical, job, and other environmental stressors (Wazqar, Kerr, Regan, & Orchard, 2017). They may also face circumstances where their personal beliefs become a challenge, but they must work for their patients' best interests. In some other cases, they are at risk of vicarious trauma or tension as they give clients and patients care services (Yu, Raphael, Mackay, Smith, & King, 2019).

Their responsibility reflects in their decision-making process, which is critical because of patients' physical and mental health needs. Hospital work is emotionally taxing. Once faced with job stress, emotional responses are called. Nurses have to use their emotions and manage them. These may put their physical and mental well-being at a disadvantage and are crucial to efficient conflict management through skills that demand high levels of emotional intelligence such as problem-solving, interpersonal relationships, and stress management.

All these activities need to be emotionally intelligent and robust. To be useful in their work, they must understand and manage their emotions like the way they cope with adversities (Basogul & Ozgur, 2016). Job satisfaction, probably the most studied attribute in the behavior of the organization, is an assessment of a person's job content (Weiss, 2002). This area assesses the perceived workplace characteristics, the working environment, and the emotional

experiences at work. If people claim they are happy with their jobs, they generally share something more like a feeling about their career than an opinion about it.

According to Tagoe and Quarshie (2016), in certain situations, the emotional quotient correlates with the work satisfaction of workers. Emotional quotient lets others understand and regulate their feelings. Hence, it helps workers take charge of their jobs. On one hand, local studies have shown that nurses, even under low levels of the practice environment, still seek pleasure from work. One can only presume possible reasons why nurses somehow manage to find contentment despite little pay, unprofitable benefits and poor support because they do not have other jobs if they leave their current job (Dones, Paguio, Bonito, Balabagno, & Pagsibigan, 2016).

This study on emotional quotient and job satisfaction is essential to be conducted to nurses to help them cope with various adversities in performing their jobs. Therefore, it is time to focus on these two different constructs and to extend the literature to the nursing profession in the Philippines; hence, this study aimed to explore if emotional quotient could be a predictor of staff nurses' job satisfaction who were working in tertiary government hospitals. Likewise, the result of this study will contribute to the improvement of job performance, productivity, and innovation of this frontline healthcare providers towards the attainment of institutional objectives and goals.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Designs

The study utilized a quantitative approach of research, particularly descriptive- evaluative, descriptive-comparative, and descriptive-correlational research designs to ascertain emotional as determinant of job satisfaction among staff nurses in central Luzon.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in four government tertiary hospitals in Central Luzon. The other hospital did not allow the researcher to subject that institution to her study. After three months, they claimed that they had not reviewed her paper for approval to conduct the study. These different institutions are all teaching and training hospitals in Central Luzon, Philippines. It states in Administrative Order No.2012-OO12 of Department of Health that Level III Hospital shall be able to deliver at least, all level 2, including but not limited to (a) the training and/or training of accredited residency hospital for doctors of 4 major specialties, namely: medicines, pediatrics, obstetrics, and gynecology and surgery.

Population and Sampling

There were 605 respondents included in the study coming from four (4) level III government hospitals in Region Central Luzon. From a pool of 750 respondents, only 605 of them were retrieved in the study with a total retrieval rate of 80.67%. Total population sampling was utilized with the following inclusion criteria: 1) licensed staff nurse; 2) currently working in a Level 3 government hospital of Central Luzon; 3) either permanent or contract of service

position; and 4) at least with one (1) year experience. Excluded were those (1) staff nurses that were on leave or absent during the conduct of study (2) head nurses or supervisors; and (3) those who worked in private tertiary hospitals. As stated by Wood and Haber (2010), the total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling where the entire population of research plan (a number of individuals collectively share common characteristics) is being studied.

Research Instrument

The study utilized adopted research tools to gather the needed data. The research instrument was comprised of two parts: Part I deals with the questions regarding Emotional Quotient which were measured using the Genos Emotional Intelligence Inventory (Genos EI). It has seven (7) components: Emotional Self-awareness; Emotional Expression; Emotional Awareness of others; Emotional Reasoning; Emotional self-management; Emotional management of others; and Emotional self-control. On this part, it will be utilizing 5-point Likert scale ranging from “almost always” to “almost never”. This is an adopted questionnaire with written permission through electronic email. The adopted instrument had undergone reliability and validity testing with the following results: self-awareness ($\alpha=0.96$), expression ($\alpha=0.82$), awareness of others ($\alpha=0.87$), reasoning ($\alpha=0.79$), self-management ($\alpha=.80$), management of others ($\alpha=0.87$), and self- control ($\alpha=0.82$).

Part II deals with the questions regarding job satisfaction which are measured using Nurse Job Satisfaction questionnaire by (Spector,1985). It is an adaptation questionnaire. It has ten (9) components: pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, co-workers, nature of work, and communication. The thirty-six- item question will be utilizing 6-point scale ranging from disagree very much to agree very much. The adopted instrument had undergone reliability and validity testing with a result of ($\alpha=0.91$).

Data Gathering Procedures

After the proposal was approved, the researcher used questionnaire from Genos Emotional Intelligence Inventory, Job Satisfaction of Spector (1985). A written request through electronic email was sent to Genos Emotional Intelligence Inventory Questionnaire in terms of approval to use the instruments. On the other hand, this study had undergone ethics review to check the content of the study. After its ethical approval, the researcher designed a letter of permission/consent along with the questionnaire regarding the conduct of the study which was addressed to staff nurses of central Luzon, Philippines. The researcher experienced the rigor of research. Research assistant helped in the collection of data. Proper instruction was given as to how to manage collected instruments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses

1.1 Self-awareness

Table 1 shows the level of the emotional quotient of nurses in terms of self-awareness. The level of awareness ranged from 4.23 to 4.42 or an average of 4.06 (SD=0.53) which indicates

that the nurses were usually aware of themselves. With a higher rating of 4.42 (SD=0.65), the nurses were aware of their body language at work. Hinzman and Kelly (2013) identified that emotional body language controls how individuals experience inand out-group interaction. On one hand, nurses were also aware of the tone of their voices when communicating with others at work; obtained a slightly higher rating of 4.39 (SD=0.28). On the other hand, having a slightly lower rating of 3.56 (SD=0.69), the respondents were usually aware of the things which upset them. The lowest rating of 3.23 (SD=0.44) indicates that the respondents sometimes find it not difficult to identify their feelings on issues at work.

The outcome is anticipated because when dealing with others, it is typical for a person to regulate emotion. The result is in line with the Daloo (2015) research, wherein supporting professionals were identified with usual emotional self-awareness having a mean score of 4.11 (SD=0.442). As supported by Stanton's research and his colleagues (2011), they discovered that psychiatrists exhibited EQ competencies, particularly, self-awareness. The standard deviation ranged from 0.41 to 0.78. A key factor for the association between nurses and clients is self-awareness. Nurses devote much of their schedule to clients than any other medical practitioner. Therefore, self-awareness can be seen as an essential component for ensuring a healthy relationship with the patient (Smith, 2006). Results from Munro's study (2011) showed that the high EQ of nurses working administrative functions is related to increased satisfaction of clients with quality healthcare.

Table 1: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Self-Awareness

Self-Awareness	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I am aware of things that upset me at work	3.56	Usually	0.69
2. I am aware of when I am feeling lnegative at work.	4.37	Usually	0.48
3. I am aware of how my feelings influence the way I respond to colleagues.	4.06	Usually	0.51
4. I am aware of my body language at work.	4.42	Usually	0.65
5. I am aware of my mood state at work.	3.92	Usually	0.28
6. I am aware of the tone of voice I use to communicate with others at work.	4.39	Usually	0.49
7. I recognise how my feelings drive my behavior at work.	4.29	Usually	0.49
8. I am aware of how my feelings influence the decisions I make at work.	4.18	Usually	0.80
9. I find it not difficult to identify my feelings on issues at work.	3.23	Sometimes	0.44
10. I am aware of things that make me feel positive at work.	4.22	Usually	0.51
Grand Weighted Mean	4.06	Usually	0.53
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.2 Expression

Table 2 reveals the level of emotional quotient of nurses in terms of expression. In terms of Expression, the overall assessment of respondents was usually expressive with a mean of 3.79 (SD=0.59). The nurses were able to share their feelings while they felt happy with the highest rating of 4.56 (SD=0.50), which is described as almost always. The finding would suggest that many Filipinos share their joy. Gestures of joy are taken according to Van Doorn, Heerdink,

and Van Kleef (2012) to indicate efficiency which is satisfactory and no added effort is needed. A slightly lower rating of 4.33 (SD=0.47), most respondents were generally able to adequately communicate their frustration if they became irritated with something. Yet little is understood as to how people respond to apparent organizational dissatisfaction.

The lowest rating of 2.97 (SD=0.85) described the nurses who sometimes did not convey how they felt about a mistaken person. With this in consideration, several studies suggest that suppression of negative emotions to elevated to stress show that writing regarding sentiments is associated with increased improvements in wellbeing. Emotional communication and an optimistic approach to life were seen to be a mutual characteristic (Beck, 2015). Presenting optimistic sentiments felt at workplace nevertheless suggested a ranking of 2.99 (SD=0.41) with classification of sometimes. This means that, given the pressure they experience in the work environment, nurses do not always communicate their affirmative feelings.

Table 2: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Expression

Expression	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I effectively express how I feel about issues at work.	4.16	Usually	0.62
2. I do not express how I feel to the wrong people at work.	2.97	Sometimes	0.85
3. I express positive emotions I experience at work appropriately.	2.99	Sometimes	0.41
4. I express how I feel at the appropriate time.	4.03	Usually	0.78
5. I provide positive feedback to colleagues.	3.84	Usually	0.65
6. When I am happy at work I express how I feel effectively.	4.56	Almost Always	0.50
7. When someone upsets me at work I express how I feel effectively.	3.29	Sometimes	0.45
8. I effectively express optimism at work.	4.29	Usually	0.46
9. I have no trouble finding the right words to express how I feel at work.	3.47	Sometimes	0.67
10. When I get frustrated with something at work I discuss my frustration appropriately.	4.33	Usually	0.47
Grand Weighted Mean	3.79	Usually	0.59
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.3 Awareness of others

Table 3 reveals the level of emotional quotient of nurses in terms of awareness of others. The respondents were usually aware of others with a weighted mean of 4.12 (SD=0.49). The average rating of 4.12 implies that the nurses were quite skilled in understanding others' emotions. With the highest rating of 4.81 (SD=0.39), the respondents almost always understood what made people feel valued at work. Rao (2012) states that leadership involves making others feel important. This was followed closely by those respondents who found it not difficult to identify the things that motivated people in the workplace with a high rating of 4.59 (SD=0.54).

The result implies that they always took into account the feelings of others. Gutwin and Greenberg's (2004) study claims that effective teamwork in a work environment requires that group members retain understanding of everyone. Individuals have to have collaborative

knowledge to identify social resources and individuals with whom to work with. Sometimes, however, respondents were aware of things that made fellow workers feel contented which had the lowest rating of 2.92 (SD= 0.31). It was obtained a nearly similar low rating of 3.15 (SD=0.84) that the nurses failed to notice when the emotional reactions of co-workers were unacceptable. Daloo (2015) found similar results, in which the nurses had lesser emotional awareness of others with a mean score of 3.95 (SD=0.475).

Table 3: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Awareness of Others

Awareness of Others	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I am aware of the things that make colleagues feel satisfied at work.	2.92	Sometimes	0.31
2. I find it not difficult to identify the things that motivate people at work.	4.59	Almost Always	0.54
3. I do not fail to identify the way people respond to me when building rapport.	4.43	Usually	0.53
4. I understand the things that cause others to feel engaged at work.	4.28	Usually	0.46
5. I demonstrate an understanding of others' feelings at work.	4.20	Usually	0.41
6. I do not fail to recognise when colleagues' emotional reactions are inappropriate.	3.15	Sometimes	0.84
7. I identify others' nonverbal emotional cues (e.g., body language).	4.19	Usually	0.39
8. I understand the things that make people feel optimistic at work.	4.30	Usually	0.48
9. I understand what makes people feel valued at work.	4.81	Almost Always	0.39
10. I identify the way people feel about issues at work.	4.38	Usually	0.49
Grand Weighted Mean	4.12	Usually	0.49
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.4 Reasoning

Table 4 shows the level of emotional quotient of nurses in terms of reasoning. The highest score or rating given by the nurses was 4.83 (SD=0.38) which describes the nurses as considering the standards of the organization when making significant decision. Values convey the principles of people and organizations. They function as a medium for decision-making in everyday behavior-guiding experiences (Barrett, 2017).

The principles of the organization must lay the groundwork for administrative actions in all fields, and it should not be taken at all layers of the organization to mean that administrative decision-making ought to be highly centralized (Iltis, 2005). The highest rating of 4.83 (SD=0.38) was closely followed by 4.76 (SD=0.43) which described nurses to consider others could respond to judgments while expressing them. The nurses considered these two parameters as very important parameters of emotional quotient.

The lowest rating the nurses received was that they seldom interacted at work in a way that caught the interest of others with a rating of 1.72 (SD=0.48). According to Ellis and Miller (2009), as cited in the study of Kokoroko and Sanda (2019), made a supportive argument that interaction exchanges that are mainly informative can enhance skill levels and improve role identification and provide comprehensive information about one's profession.

People with good EQ skills make more effective use of emotions to reason. Reasoning by correctly utilizing feelings is a fundamental skill in establishing a relationship with clients. As some nursing studies indicate, it can be that what nurses often refer to as "intuition" or "trusting your gut" would be this ability to reasonably "think / feel" using emotions.

The overall mean of nurses' emotional quotient is 3.51 (SD= 0.48) and is described as usually.

Table 4: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Reasoning

Reasoning	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I ask others how they feel about different solutions when problem solving at work.	3.72	Usually	0.45
2. I demonstrate to others that I have considered their feelings in decisions I make at work.	4.45	Usually	0.50
3. I consider the organisation's values when making important decisions.	4.83	Almost Always	0.38
4. I demonstrate to others that I have considered my own feelings when making decisions at work.	4.23	Usually	0.71
5. I communicate decisions at work in a way that captures other's attention	1.72	Seldom	0.48
6. I gain stakeholders' commitment to decisions I make at work.	3.23	Sometimes	0.43
7. I appropriately communicate decisions to stakeholders.	2.53	Sometimes	0.62
8. I consider the way others may react to decisions when communicating them.	4.76	Almost Always	0.43
9. I take into account both technical information and the way I feel about different choices when making decisions at work.	3.80	Usually	0.40
10. I do not focus solely on facts and technical information related to problems when trying to derive a solution.	1.79	Seldom	0.41
Grand Weighted Mean	3.51	Usually	0.48
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.5 Self-management

Table 5 shows the level of emotional quotient in terms of self-management. An average of 3.64 (SD=0.49) and a description of usually was obtained which indicates that the nurses were average in terms of self-management. The findings of Cecil and Glass (2015) showed that the emotional "self-management" was an important advantage to allow adequate care to be provided although it leads to emotional confinement.

The authors further point out that it was a conditioned response used to care for oneself and was crucial in emotional imbalance situations. The emotional quotient of nurses in terms of adjustment to new conditions had the highest rating of 4.73 (SD=0.45) with a description of almost always. An individual should recognize that change occurs and uses his right to decide what to do next (Tasler, 2016).

The lower rating of 4.20 (SD=0.43) where nurses responded to events that frustrated them was usually lower. The lowest rating of 1.70 (SD=0.46) was obtained which identified nurses to seldom ruminate about things that angered them at work.

Table 5: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Self-Management

Self-Management	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I do not take criticism from colleagues personally.	3.66	Usually	0.63
2. I engage in activities that make me feel positive at work.	3.87	Usually	0.55
3. I do not ruminate about things that anger me at work.	1.70	Seldom	0.46
4. I effectively deal with things that annoy me at work.	4.44	Usually	0.50
5. I appropriately respond to colleagues who frustrate me at work.	3.41	Sometimes	0.50
6. I demonstrate positive moods and emotions at work.	3.64	Usually	0.49
7. I quickly adjust to new conditions at work.	4.73	Almost Always	0.45
8. I handle stressful situations at work effectively.	3.62	Usually	0.49
9. I respond to events that frustrate me appropriately.	4.20	Usually	0.43
10. I explore the causes of things that mupset me at work.	3.13	Sometimes	0.41
Grand Weighted Mean	3.64	Usually	0.49
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.6 Management of others

Table 6 shows the level of emotional quotient of nurses in terms of management of others. The nurses almost always created a positive working environment for others which got the highest rating of 4.68 (SD=0.47). Based on the study of Latham, Hogan, and Ringl (2008), devoted nurses do not only support their fellow nurses, but also help to improve the overall working situation. On the other hand, nurses can get colleagues to cooperate with almost similar highest rating of 4.60 (SD= 0.51).

A highly effective approach to promote teamwork and coordination is to create opportunities for various groups to simply get along. Such interactions between groups can be formal or informal. Promoting honest discussion, joint meetings, the introduction of preop and postop team gatherings and the formation of interdisciplinary assemblies or working groups that regularly address areas of concern provide an immediate approach that reduces the chances of adverse incidents (O'Daniel & Rosenstein, 2008).

On the other hand, the nurses sometimes helped people deal with issues that caused them frustration at work and this was rated the lowest by the nurses having a rating of 3.14 (SD=0.35). This finding implies that nurses did not meddle on the problems of their colleagues. They were more concerned on what made them happy.

The result was almost similar to helping them feel differently about the situation when colleagues were disappointed with a rating of 3.35 (SD=0.49). The findings of Daloos (2015) indicate higher level of emotional intelligence among helping professionals when it comes to management of others. The overall assessment was usually aware with overall mean of 3.99 (SD=0.48).

Table 6: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Management of Others

Management of Others	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I create a positive working environment for others.	4.68	Almost Always	0.47
2. I get colleagues to cooperate.	4.60	Almost Always	0.51
3. I motivate others toward work related goals.	3.90	Usually	0.30
4. When necessary I effectively demonstrate empathy to colleagues	3.84	Usually	0.63
5. I am effective in helping others feel positive at work.	4.15	Usually	0.57
6. I help people find effective ways of responding to upsetting events.	4.11	Usually	0.58
7. When colleagues are disappointed about something I help them feel differently about the situation.	3.35	Sometimes	0.49
8. I help people deal with issues that cause them frustration at work.	3.14	Sometimes	0.35
9. I do know what to do or say when colleagues get upset at work.	4.08	Usually	0.54
10. I resolve emotional situations at work effectively.	4.05	Usually	0.41
Grand Weighted Mean	3.99	Usually	0.48
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

1.7 Self-control

Table 7 shows the level of emotional quotient of nurses in terms of self-control. With the highest rating of 4.91 (SD=0.29), the nurses almost always remained focused when anxious about something at work.

This was followed closely by the rating of 4.84 (SD=0.37) which identifies the nurses to almost always think clearly even when upset. Another parameter of EQ of self-control to have the highest rating was the rating of 4.68 (SD=0.48) which described the nurses to demonstrate excitement at work. On the other hand, the lowest rating of 3.26 (SD=0.48) was indicated by the nurses that they are sometimes patient when things don't get done as planned at work.

This particular result is in contrary to the theory of Guthrie and Azores (1986) as cited in the study of Daloo (2015) when they asserted that Filipinos possess emotional control. According to them, Filipinos have an impressive attitude of controlling emotions in times of negative experiences. The overall assessment was usually aware with overall mean of 3.96 (SD=0.41).

The overall emotional intelligence would describe the respondents being engaged in a variety of emotionally intelligent behavior.

Table 7: Level of Emotional Quotient of Nurses in Terms of Self-Control

Self-Control	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1.iiI demonstrate enthusiasm appropriately at work.	4.22	Usually	0.41
2. I remain focused when anxious about something at work.	4.91	Almost Always	0.29
3. I behave appropriately when angry at work.	3.89	Usually	0.46
4.iiI demonstrate excitement at work appropriately.	4.68	Almost Always	0.48
5. When I am under stress, I do not become impulsive.	3.81	Usually	0.41
6. I control my temper at work.	3.94	Usually	0.26
7. I hold back my initial reaction when something upsets me at work.	3.68	Usually	0.48
8. iI am patient when things don't get done as planned at work.	3.26	Sometimes	0.48
9. When upset at work I still think clearly.	4.84	Almost Always	0.37
10. I keep calm in difficult situations at work.	3.63	Usually	0.49
Grand Weighted Mean	4.09	Usually	0.41
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Almost Never, 1.50-2.49 Seldom, 2.50-3.49 Sometimes, 3.50-4.49 Usually, 4.50-5.00 Almost Always</i>			

2. Assessment on the Level of Job Satisfaction among nurses

2.1 Pay

Table 8 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of pay. The nurses exhibited a slight level of job dissatisfaction in terms of pay as indicated in a mean of 2.53 (SD=0.51). The highest rating of 2.97 (SD=0.37) indicates that the nurses slightly disagreed when asked if paid a fair amount for the work they did. This is followed by a lower rating of 2.43 (SD=0.69) which indicates that nurses moderately disagreed that raises or increase in salary were not too few and far between. Salaries of nurses or medical employees in the Philippines are considered low compared to other countries.

However, yearly salary increases have been given starting 5 years ago. A similar finding conducted by Kwak, Chung, Xu and Eun-Jung (2010) stated that executives and staffs classified ten essential factors affecting their job satisfaction and its main aspects were good relations in the work environment, followed by salary, recognition from their supervisors, career advancement, learning opportunities, motivation of supervisors to employment, better working conditions, work and professional difficulties, and job-related freedom. With a rating of 2.38 (SD=0.49), nurses moderately disagreed that they were contented with the wage increase that the government is providing despite the salary standardization being given every year.

They also disagreed that they were being compensated well in terms of the amount of load they did. With a rating of 2.35 (SD=0.48), they indicated that they moderately disagreed when asked if appreciated when they thought about what the organization would pay them.

Table 8: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Pay

Pay	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	2.97	Disagree Slightly	0.37
2. iRaises are not too few and far between.	2.43	Disagree Moderately	0.69
3. I feel appreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me	2.35	Disagree Moderately	0.48
4. I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	2.38	Disagree Moderately	0.49
Grand Weighted Mean	2.53	Disagree Slightly	0.51
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.2 Promotion

Table 9 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of promotion. The overall assessment is “disagree slightly” with overall mean of 3.79 (SD=0.47) in terms of promotion. With the highest rating of 4.92 (SD=0.28), nurses moderately agreed or highly satisfied that people get ahead as fast here as they do in other places. They also agreed slightly that there is really too many chances for promotion on job with a mean of 4.08 (SD=0.60). There are common rules and regulations for employee promotion, which are laid down by the Civil Service and the Department of Budget and Management (DBM). The lowest weighted mean of 2.83 (SD=0.52) indicates that the nurses slightly disagreed that those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted. They do not agree that those who work hard will be promoted. The study of Lorber and Skela Savič (2012) found that promotion opportunities are the fourth most important element affecting employee satisfaction and leadership. However, this is contradicted by Sveinsdottir, Biering, and Ramel (2006) who found that workers were least contented with promotion. In the Philippines, promotion in the government service like the hospitals is difficult unless one employee retires. Even as civil servants' wages seem to be sufficient, the government still provides constrained plantilla placements that hinder hospitals from hiring more permanent employees and employing contract employees instead. According to Malik, Danish, and Munir (2012), the only sure source of job satisfaction is pay and promotion in developing countries like Pakistan where there is high unemployment and destabilization of economy. In the government hospitals, nurses slightly disagreed that there is less opportunity for promotion in their work, those who do well at work have a decent chance of becoming promoted.

Table 9: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Promotion

Promotion	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. There is really too many chances for promotion on my job	4.08	Agree Slightly	0.60
2. Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	2.83	Disagree Slightly	0.52
3. People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places	4.92	Agree Moderately	0.28
4. I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	3.32	Disagree Slightly	0.47
Grand Weighted Mean	3.79	Agree Slightly	0.47
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.3 Supervision

Table 10 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of supervision. With an average rating of 4.56 (SD=0.44), the nurses were moderately satisfied as to the supervision provided by their supervisors. They moderately agreed that their supervisors were equipped with the necessary skills making them competent in their jobs. Hence, the highest rating of 5.56 was given by the nurses which they moderately agreed that their supervisors were quite competent in doing their job. The nurses also gave a rating of 4.88 which indicates that they liked their supervisors. According to Panchal's study (2016), supervision translates to a moderate job satisfaction rating since employees are fairly satisfied with their job guidance. Relationship with that of the direct supervisor, as well as the expected competence and integrity of the superior in an administrative role, may influence the employees' motivation, that could result in the positive or negative feeling they have for their work. This is confirmed by Abdullah, Uli, and Salahudin's (2009) study, which reported that superiors with a positive behavior would demonstrate their empathy about the challenges of the workers and took proper involvement in the workers, and all of these encouraging acts could consequently contribute to job satisfaction. Furthermore, Tierney, Bauer, and Potter's (2002) study also showed that workers grow out to be incredibly efficient when they believe that the guidance extended to them is adequate and this also improves their degree of satisfaction. Superiors and workers rated ten most important aspects affecting their job satisfaction and the most significant elements were positive relationships in the work environment, followed by salary, superiors' appreciation, growth opportunities, learning opportunities, motivation of supervisors to work, decent working environment, work and professional constraints, and work-related freedom and independence (Lorber and Skela Savič, 2012). Likewise, the lowest rating was 3.87 (SD=0.34) where the nurses slightly agreed that the supervisors were fair to them. Moreover, nurses slightly agreed that their supervisors showed too much interest in the feeling of their subordinates.

Table 10: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Supervision

Supervision	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.	5.56	Agree Moderately	0.51
2. My supervisor is fair to me.	3.87	Agree Slightly	0.34
3. My supervisor shows too much interest in the feelings of subordinates.	3.94	Agree Slightly	0.25
4. I like my supervisor.	4.88	Agree Moderately	0.68
Grand Weighted Mean	4.56	Agree Moderately	0.44
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.4 Fringe Benefits

Table 11 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of fringe benefits. With an average rating of 3.03 (SD=0.18), the nurses were slightly satisfied as to fringe benefit. With the highest rating of 4.24 (SD=0.43), they slightly agreed with the benefits they received, that the benefits they received were as good as most organizations offer followed by "The benefit

package that we have is equitable” (WM=4.10, SD=0.85) which they “agreed slightly”. The benefits provided the same package of fringe benefits to all government hospitals except the private hospitals. The nurses indicated slight satisfaction as to the fringe benefits being provided by the government. With a rating of 4.10 (SD=0.85), they slightly agreed with the benefits they received, that the benefits they received was true to other hospitals and the benefit package was equitable. Similar finding was found by Khamlub et al. (2013) that the respondents were highly satisfied in terms of additional compensation for work. Nurses gave a lower rating of 3.03 (SD=0.18) where they slightly disagreed that they were satisfied with the benefits they received. Nurses receive the benefits for health workers such as allowances, hazard pay, bonuses, and others given by the government. Government nurses are more satisfied than private nurses (Aggari, 2019).

Table 11: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Fringe Benefit

Fringe Benefit	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I am satisfied with the benefits I receive.	3.03	Disagree Slightly	0.18
2. The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	4.24	Agree Slightly	0.43
3. The benefit package that we have is equitable.	4.10	Agree Slightly	0.85
4. There are benefits we do have which we should have.	3.54	Agree Slightly	0.51
Grand Weighted Mean	3.73	Agree Slightly	0.49
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.5 Contingent Rewards

Table 12 presents the level of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of contingent rewards. The level of job satisfaction of nurses as to giving of contingent rewards was agreed slightly as indicated in the rating of 4.40 (SD=0.59) since they slightly agreed that “when you do a good job you receive a recognition for it”. Similar findings were shown by Artz (2010) in which higher levels of satisfaction with workers are associated with significant performance measures like the lower leave and the absenteeism, possibly as a result of provisions on fringes. With a rating of 3.22 (SD=0.42), the nurses slightly disagreed that they felt their efforts were rewarded the way they should be. The study of Gu, Zhen, Song, and Xu (2019) supports this finding since the respondents of their study had low work satisfaction in terms of rewards. Considering the numerous tasks, they did in the hospitals, they felt that they were not compensated for their efforts. On the other hand, the nurses slightly agreed that when they had a good job, they received acknowledgement. They slightly disagreed also that they thought that the work was valued and they did not feel that the hard work was remunerated considering the numerous tasks they did in the hospitals. The lowest rating of 2.21 (SD=0.41) indicates that the nurses moderately disagreed that there are many rewards given to those who work in the hospitals. The overall assessment was “disagree slightly” with overall mean of 3.15 (SD=0.46). This assertion is in line with Behera, Sahoo, and Sundaray’s (2011) research that fringe benefits such as health coverage, vacations, and other perks may influence employees' satisfaction ratings. A HR Focus report (2007) as cited in Yvonne, Husna Abdull Rahman, and Sang Long

(2014) found that “fringe benefit “and other incentives have been rated as the most significant determinants with job satisfaction. Therefore, the dimension of it is assumed to be as significant as the other dimensions such as compensation, promotions, contingent incentives, operating conditions, and interaction in job satisfaction analysis. In contrast with Terera and Ngirande's (2014) analysis of the effect of incentives on job satisfaction and retention, it reveals that employee benefits increase in employee retention but do not lead to job satisfaction.

Table 12: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Contingent Rewards

Contingent Rewards	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. When I do a good job, I receive a recognition for it that I should receive.	4.40	Agree Slightly	0.59
2. I do feel that the work I do is appreciated.	3.22	Disagree Slightly	0.42
3. There are several rewards for those who work here.	2.21	Disagree Moderately	0.41
4. I feel that my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	2.77	Disagree Slightly	0.42
Grand Weighted Mean	3.15	Disagree Slightly	0.46
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.6 Operating Conditions

Table 13 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of the operating conditions. The nurses showed a moderate level of satisfaction in terms of operating conditions with the highest rating of 4.79 (SD=0.41) where they moderately agreed that their efforts in doing good were seldom blocked by red tape. They also agreed that many of rules and procedures were making their job easy (WM=4.23, SD=0.45). The average rating of 4.07 (SD= 0.42) indicated a slight satisfaction of the nurses in terms of operating conditions. This conclusion is similar to Al-Zu’bi’s (2010) finding that college lecturers in Pakistan have been reasonably satisfied with operating conditions. On the other hand, nurse respondents disagreed slightly that they did not have much to do at work with a mean of 3.40 (SD= 0.49). Al-Dossari, Vail, and Macfarlane (2012) found that their work conditions did not satisfy nurses. Related findings were obtained by Gu, Zhen, Song and Xu (2019) who discovered that the physicians in Shandong Province of China were not satisfied with their working conditions.

Table 13: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Operating Conditions

Operating Conditions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job easy.	4.23	Agree Slightly	0.45
2. My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.	4.79	Agree Moderately	0.41
3. I don’t have too much to do at work.	3.40	Disagree Slightly	0.49
4. I don’t have too much paperwork.	3.89	Agree Slightly	0.31
Grand Weighted Mean	4.08	Agree Slightly	0.42
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.7 Co-workers

Table 14 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of Co-workers. The level of satisfaction of nurses in working with co-workers had the highest rating of 5.34 (SD=0.48). The nurses moderately agreed that they enjoyed their co-worker.

The nurse-respondents also moderately agreed that they did not have to work harder at their job because of the competence of their colleagues (WM= 4.06 SD= 0.26). The nurses also moderately agreed that they did not have to work harder because their co-workers were competent with a mean of 4.51 (SD= 0.61). Similar findings were found by Khamlub et al. (2013) and Sveinsdottir, Biering, and Ramel (2006) that nurses were highly satisfied working with co-workers. Accordingly, Lorber and Skela Savič (2012) found that good relations in the work environment are the most important elements that impact job satisfaction.

They indicated that they enjoyed working with other nurses. However, according to Parvin (2011), the study found the employee satisfaction level in terms of ties with colleagues "neither pleased nor unhappy." The lowest rating of 4.06 (SD=0.26) indicates that nurses slightly agreed there is little bickering and fighting at work. This supports the study of Khamisa, Oldenburg, Peltzer, and Ilic (2015) which suggests that level of stress encountered by nurses affects personnel's issues, including the work of colleagues.

This negates the study of Parker (2017) stating that 18 percent of them in a survey with 4,000 nurses said that a nurse abused them verbally. This type of bickering is unfortunately very damaging to keeping the team working.

The average rating of 4.53 (SD= 0.47) indicated moderate satisfaction of the nurses in terms of workers. Sveinsdottir, Biering, and Ramel (2006) also obtained similar results, showing that nurses are most pleased with colleagues and head nursing staff and less satisfied with their prospects for advancement.

Table 14: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Co-workers

Co-workers	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I like the people I work with.	4.22	Agree Slightly	0.52
2. I find I don't have to work harder at my job because of the competence of people I work with.	4.51	Agree Moderately	0.61
3. I enjoy my coworkers.	5.34	Agree Moderately	0.48
4. There is little bickering and fighting at work.	4.06	Agree Slightly	0.26
Grand Weighted Mean	4.53	Agree Moderately	0.47
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.8 Nature of work

Table 15 resents the level of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of nature of work. The average rating of 3.81 (SD=0.52) given with a description of slightly agree by the nurses implies a slight level of job satisfaction in terms of nature of work. Nursing is needed in work environments with minimal resources and expanded obligations, and the provision of humane, emphatic,

economic, professional, and ethical care. The disparity between high-quality care and stressful work conditions can contribute to exhaustion. With the highest rating of 4.76 (SD=0.43), nurses moderately agreed that they liked doing things they did at work. They also slightly agreed that they did not feel that their job was meaningless (WM=4.46, SD=0.73). This confirms the finding of Khamlub et al. (2013) that the nurses were highly satisfied in their job with a rating of 4.88. On the other hand, with the lowest rating of 2.77 (SD=0.49), they, however, slightly disagreed when asked that their job was enjoyable since they also provided service to the people. Khamisa, Oldenburg, Peltzer, and Ilic (2015) stressed that the nature of job could contribute to exhaustion.

Table 15: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Nature of Work

Nature of Work	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. I don't feel my job is meaningless.	4.46	Agree Slightly	0.73
2. I like doing the things I do at work.	4.76	Agree Moderately	0.43
3. I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.	3.24	Disagree Slightly	0.44
4. My job is enjoyable.	2.77	Disagree Slightly	0.49
Grand Weighted Mean	3.81	Agree Slightly	0.52
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agree Very Much</i>			

2.9 Communication

Table 16 shows the rating of Job Satisfaction of nurses in terms of communication. The average rating of 3.90 (SD=0.56) given with a description of slightly agree by the nurses implies a slight level of job satisfaction in terms of communication. The highest rating of 4.30 (SD=0.46) indicates that nurses slightly agreed that communication seemed good within their organization. Communication in an organization is very important especially between supervisors and subordinates and even among the nurses themselves.

Hombrados-Miendieta and Cosano- Rivas (2011) established the significant role of workers and supervisor support in order to ensure employee satisfaction. Similar rating of 4.30 (SD=0.46) was given by nurses that they slightly agreed that the goals of the organization were clear to them. The lowest rating of 3.44 (SD=0.80) indicates that the nurses slightly disagreed that they often felt that they know what was going on with the organization.

Their jobs as nurses in the hospitals was critical so they were fully aware of their work assignments. These findings reinforced the conclusion by Pincus (2006) as cited in Ramirez (2012) that the superior, assistant communication relationship is the most crucial factor in subordinate work satisfaction and that the perceptions of the employee's supervisory communication can also be significantly affecting employee satisfaction.

Table 16: Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Communication

Communication	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	SD
1. Communications seem good within mmthis organization.	4.30	Agree Slightly	0.46
2. The goals of this organization are mmclear to me.	4.30	Agree Slightly	0.47
3. I often feel that I do know what is mmgoing on with the organization.	3.44	Disagree Slightly	0.80
4.iWork assignments are fully mmexplained.	3.57	Agree Slightly	0.50
Grand Weighted Mean	3.90	Agree Slightly	0.56
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.49 Disagree Very Much, 1.50-2.49 Disagree Moderately, 2.50-3.49 Disagree Slightly, 3.50-4.49 Agree Slightly, 4.50-5.49 Agree Moderately, 5.50-6.00 Agee Very Much</i>			

Association of Job Satisfaction to Emotional Quotient

Table 17 presents the association of job satisfaction to emotional quotient of respondents. Between "self-awareness" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.40, with a qualitative description of low relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "self-awareness". It can be deduced from the results that if self-awareness of nurses is improved, job satisfaction can also be increased. It supports the study of Kiani, Iftikhar, & Ahmed (2016), which points to a link between self-awareness and employee satisfaction.

The nurses need to make adjustment to their weaknesses to improve themselves; hence, improving their job performance. Between "expression" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.63, with a qualitative description of moderate relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "expression". Research on job satisfaction suggests that emotional expression has positive and negative results, depending on the type of emotional expression displayed performed by employees (Xiaochen, Phiri, Tahseen, & Mapiye 2018). Between "awareness of others" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.30, with a qualitative description of low relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.017 is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "awareness of others". According to Anjum (2014), social skills or awareness of others' feelings and concerns are linked to satisfaction with job. Between "reasoning" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.27, with a qualitative description of low relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "reasoning". It can be inferred that, if a person can manage decision making at work, this can increase his satisfaction level. The research by Coetzer (2013) supports the fact that the emotional quotient is associated with satisfaction at work. Between "self-

management" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.36, with a qualitative description of low relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "self-management". It can be deduced from the results that if a person can manage himself, this can improve his level of job satisfaction.

It supports the study of Joy, Anah, and Ejike (2019) which indicates that the attributes and methods of job self-management have an important and positive effect on employee satisfaction including nurses. Between "management of others" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.69, with a qualitative description of moderate relationship proved to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "management of others". From the findings, it can be deduced that nurses with a higher level of emotional intelligence are happier, more productive and have greater job satisfaction (Aghayar, Sharifi, & Sharifi, 2006 as cited in the study of Emdady & Bagheri, 2013). Employees with a greater range of emotional intelligence are more comfortable in work with more control with fewer people in those areas telling what to do and perform more. Finally, between "self-control" and job satisfaction, the computed correlation coefficient of 0.22, with a qualitative description of low relationship is proven to be significant, since the computed P-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, there is a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient of respondents as to "self-control". The findings and initial analysis of Dou, Nie, Wang, and Liu (2016) offer additional evidence of the positive relationship between self-control and work satisfaction. This supports the study conducted by Shukla, Adhikari, and Ray (2016), which found that only self-control was significantly linked to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is found to mediate this relationship. Workers with higher levels of job satisfaction have high emotional intelligence because they assess and control their own emotions relative to workers with lower emotional intelligence according to the findings.

Table 17: Association of Job Satisfaction to Emotional Quotient of Respondents

Emotional Quotient	Job Satisfaction			
	Correlation Coefficient	Qualitative Description	P-Value	Remark
Self-Awareness	0.40	Low Relationship	0.000	Significant
Expression	0.63	Moderate Relationship	0.000	Significant
Awareness of Others	0.30	Low Relationship	0.017	Significant
Reasoning	0.27	Low Relationship	0.000	Significant
Self-Management	0.36	Low Relationship	0.000	Significant
Management of Others	0.69	Moderate Relationship	0.000	Significant
Self-Control	0.22	Low Relationship	0.000	Significant
Legend: 0.00 No Relationship, +0.00-+0.20 Negligible Relationship, +0.21-+0.40 Low Relationship, +0.41-+0.70 Moderate Relationship, +0.71-+0.90 High Relationship, +0.91-+0.99 Very High Relationship, +1 Perfect Relationship, Significant at P<0.05				

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The emotional quotient of the nurse-respondents revealed that they usually possessed self-awareness, expression, awareness of others, reasoning, self-management, management of others, and self-control, respectively.
2. Nurses agreed moderately on their job satisfaction toward supervision and co-workers. They agreed slightly on Promotion, Fringe Benefit, Nature of Work, Communication, and operating condition. However, they disagreed slightly toward contingent rewards and pay.
3. It was also shown that there was a significant association between job satisfaction and emotional quotient.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Since the level of job satisfaction among the nurses in terms of fringe benefits and contingent awards was relatively lower, the findings of this study may provide inputs to come up with a policy or recommendation to increase the existing benefits for them. Giving of awards to hard working or outstanding nurses may also be given in accordance with the Civil Service guidelines on the merit award.
2. Human Resources of Hospitals are encouraged to develop intervention programs to help nurses express and manage their emotions to minimize stress and burnout. A seminar on emotional quotient and communication among nurses may be conducted to nurses to strengthen and enrich their self-awareness, awareness of others, reasoning, self-management, management of others, and self-control.
3. Another study related maybe conducted among nurses in the private level III hospitals in Region III to see the findings that may surface.

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